

Mendeley Data HardwareX Submission Instructions

July 24, 2019

For more detailed information about using Mendeley Data view their [FAQ](#).

Notes

- 10 GB max repository size. If more space is required, [Zenodo](#) offers 50 GB.
- HardwareX manuscripts are submitted separately in [Editorial Manager](#).

Publishing a Mendeley Data repository for a [HardwareX](#) Submission

1. Create an account on [Mendeley Data](#) if you do not already have one.
2. Create a new dataset: <https://data.mendeley.com/drafts/new>
3. Insert the title of your HardwareX manuscript.
4. Add authors as contributors to the dataset.
5. In the “Description” field, insert your HardwareX abstract. In addition describe the design files that will be included here.
6. Upload all relevant design files, code, research data, and supplemental information to your HardwareX manuscript submission. This can be done directly from your computer. We recommend you organize the files in folders (“Software”, “CAD files”, and etc.).
7. Optional: Add the relevant institutions if they are listed.
8. Add the categories for the data. (at minimum one category is required)
9. Select a license that is compatible with HardwareX.

[More information on compatible licenses](#). These are defined by the [Open-Source Hardware Association](#) (OSHW). Notably, non-commercial licenses are not allowed (see the [OSHW FAQ](#) for details). If you need an exception contact the editors prior to submitting.

Incorporating your Mendeley Data repository into your [HardwareX](#) Submission

1. Once you have created your repository you can share it in your submission in a Public or Embargoed way. They are described below.

Public: Once your repository is ready for sharing. Hit publish. Do not embargo it! The Project's DOI can be found on the right side of the page.

Embargoed: Set an embargo date up to one year then hit publish. The project's DOI can be found on the right side of the page.

Generate your “Embargoed-link”: Hit the “Share” button at the bottom of your published repository, it will produce your “Embargoed-link” that peer reviewers and editors can use to review your submission. You will submit this link on Editorial Manger during submission.

2. Insert your Project DOI URL (not your embargoed link!) throughout your HardwareX manuscript as required (e.g. “Specification Table”, “Design Files”, and etc.). We recommend doing so as a URL by inserting “<https://doi.org/>” before your DOI, for example <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3356702>.
3. When submitting your HardwareX submission on [Editorial Manager](#) insert the “Embargoed-Link” and “Project DOI URI” in the “Additional Information” section of submission interface.

Updating your Mendeley Data Repository

If necessary in a revision, the Mendeley Data repository can be easily updated with a new version.

1. Login into your Mendeley Data account and go to your project page.
2. Modify your data using the same process
3. Then publish.
4. DO NOT CHANGE THE DOI

If the DOI is accidentally changed, be sure to update all repository links throughout your manuscript.